

A MICROMECHANICAL MODEL IN CYCLIC PLASTICITY FOR PERIODIC WAVY COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, a micromechanical model based on the parametric finite-volume direct averaging micromechanics (FVDAM) theory and the Abdel-Karim-Ohno cyclic constitutive model was built to simulate the cyclic behavior of periodic composites with wavy microstructure. Despite the increased use of this kind of materials, little work has been done in investigating the cyclic plasticity response of periodic wavy composites. Unit cell with hard elastic phase and soft elastoplastic phase is built to characterize the micro and macro response under unidirectional strain controlled cyclic loading. By introducing the cyclic plasticity constitutive relation in the soft phase of the composite material, the mean stress relaxation phenomenon is simulated. The homogenized as well as the localized response of two kinds of wavy composites is investigated with consideration of different volume fraction and amplitude-to-wavelength ratios.

1 INTRODUCTION

Wavy microstructure occurs in many nature and manufactured composite materials. In nature, nacre, outer shell of mollusk and antler bone are all found with the wavy microstructure, which provide a better mechanical properties. These kind of natural materials have inspired the designed of man-made composite materials. For instance, wavy thin metallic and ceramic multilayer material in nanotechnology can be used for magnetic, optoelectronic and high-speed electronic applications [1].

During the past ten years, many researches have been done to investigate the composite materials with wavy microstructures. Khatam and Pindera [1-3] investigated the homogenized and localized response of periodic material with elastic and elastic-plastic wavy layer, their works are under consideration of factors such as thermal effect, volume fraction of hard phase and ply waviness, in both small and large deformation. Katz et al. [4] analyzed the wavy brick-and-mortar architectures by different waviness and shift patterns. Tu and Pindera [5] simulated the finite-deformation response of three types of heart-valve chordae tendineae with bio-inspired material architectures.

While the properties of wavy lamellar architectures have been studied extensively, little work has been reported concerning the cyclic plastic behavior of composites with wavy microstructure. Therefore, in this paper, we focus on the cyclic mean stress relaxation of wavy composites by different amplitude-to-wavelength ratio. Two types of wavy materials are investigated (Figure 1), fiber reinforced wavy material and multilayer wavy material, where the dark grey represents the elastic hard phase and the light grey part is elastoplastic soft phase. The homogenization and the localization analysis are based on the parametric finite volume direct averaging micromechanics (FVDAM) theory combined with the Ohno-Wang cyclic plasticity constitutive model.

The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 is a brief summary of the framework of the parametric finite volume direct averaging micromechanics(FVDAM). The process of introducing the Abdel-Karim-Ohno constitutive model[6] into the FVDAM framework is demonstrated in Section 3. Section 4 gives the numerical results of the homogenized and localized response of two different wavy composites, and the influence of volume fraction and amplitude-to-wavelength ratios. Section 5 provides the summary of the results and pertinent conclusions.

Figure 1: Two types of wavy composites with highlighted unit cell.

2 PARAMETRIC FVDAM THEORY

The parametric finite-volume direct averaging micromechanics (FVDAM) theory is a homogenization method enabling the calculation of a unit cell problem. The theory is originally proposed by Bansal and Pindera [7] for fluid and solid problems. It has been further extended to be an attractive alternative to the prevalent finite-element approach for modeling composite materials. Details of the parametric theory framework has been illustrated in a sequence of papers, originating from Gattu et al. [8], and Khatam and Pindera [9], and summarized by Cavalcante et al. [10] and Chen et al. [11]. The simulation of homogenized and localized mechanical response using FVDAM theory has a comparable accuracy to the finite-element method but with a better efficiency.

The parametric FVDAM is based on the discretization of the unit cell of a periodic material, in this case, we chose the smallest repeated wavy unit from the composites as in Figure 1. Unlike the rectangular discretization of the standard FVDAM, parametric FVDAM generates the q th subvolume in the η - ξ reference coordinates bounded by $-1 \leq \eta \leq +1$ and $-1 \leq \xi \leq +1$, which can be translated into actual reference y_2 - y_3 by applying the coordinate transformation as in Figure 2.

$$y_i^{(q)}(\eta, \xi) = \sum_{j=1}^4 N_j(\eta, \xi) y_i^{(j,q)}, i = 2, 3 \quad (1)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} N_1(\eta, \xi) &= (1/4)(1-\eta)(1-\xi), & N_2(\eta, \xi) &= (1/4)(1+\eta)(1-\xi) \\ N_3(\eta, \xi) &= (1/4)(1+\eta)(1+\xi), & N_4(\eta, \xi) &= (1/4)(1-\eta)(1+\xi) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

The vertices $(y_2^{(p,q)}, y_3^{(p,q)})$ of the q th subvolume are numbered in a counterclockwise manner starting from the lower left corner for $p=1, 2, 3, 4$. The orientation of the face F_p is determined by the unit normal vector $\mathbf{n}^{(p,q)} = [n_2^{(p,q)} n_3^{(p,q)}]$ where

$$n_2^{(p,q)} = \frac{y_3^{(p+1,q)} - y_3^{(p,q)}}{\sqrt{(y_2^{(p+1,q)} - y_2^{(p,q)})^2 + (y_3^{(p+1,q)} - y_3^{(p,q)})^2}}, n_3^{(p,q)} = \frac{y_2^{(p+1,q)} - y_2^{(p,q)}}{\sqrt{(y_2^{(p+1,q)} - y_2^{(p,q)})^2 + (y_3^{(p+1,q)} - y_3^{(p,q)})^2}} \quad (3)$$

where $p=1, 2, 3, 4$ and when $p=4$, $p+1 \rightarrow 1$

Figure 2: Parametric mapping.

Following the framework of homogenization theory[12], the displacement distribution in q th subvolume can be represented by the two-scale expansion in the slow scale \mathbf{x} and fast scale \mathbf{y} , containing macroscopic and fluctuating components:

$$u_i^{(q)}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) = \bar{\varepsilon}_{ij} x_j + u_i'^{(q)}(\mathbf{y}) \quad (4)$$

Then the local strain-displacement relations can be obtained in the form

$$\varepsilon_{ij}^{(q)} = \bar{\varepsilon}_{ij} + \varepsilon_{ij}'^{(q)} = \bar{\varepsilon}_{ij} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial u_i'^{(q)}}{\partial y_j} + \frac{\partial u_j'^{(q)}}{\partial y_i} \right) \quad (5)$$

where the fluctuating displacement components $u_i'^{(q)}$ ($i=1,2,3$) are approximated by the 2nd-order Legendre-type polynomial expansion in the reference coordinates $\eta-\xi$ under the generalized plane strain constraint, which means $\bar{\varepsilon}_{11} = \bar{\varepsilon}_{11}^{(q)}$ for all subvolumes under all loading conditions

$$u_i'^{(q)} = W_{i(00)}^{(q)} + \eta W_{i(10)}^{(q)} + \xi W_{i(01)}^{(q)} + \frac{1}{2} (3\eta^2 - 1) W_{i(20)}^{(q)} + \frac{1}{2} (3\xi^2 - 1) W_{i(02)}^{(q)} \quad (6)$$

where $W_{i(mn)}^{(q)}$ are unknown coefficients which can be expressed in terms of the surface-averaged displacement $\hat{u}_i^{(p,q)}$ in the end.

The surface-averaged displacements $\hat{u}_i^{(p,q)}$ and the surface-averaged tractions $\hat{t}_i^{(p,q)}$ of four faces of the subvolume can be calculated by integrating along the four faces ($\eta = \pm 1$ and $\xi = \pm 1$) in reference coordinates $\eta-\xi$

for ($p=1,3$):

$$\hat{u}_i^{(p,q)} = \frac{1}{2} \int_{-1}^1 u_i'^{(q)}(\eta, \mp 1) d\eta, \quad \hat{t}_i^{(p,q)} = \frac{1}{2} \int_{-1}^1 t_i^{(q)}(\eta, \mp 1) d\eta \quad (7)$$

for ($p=2,4$):

$$\hat{u}_i^{(p,q)} = \frac{1}{2} \int_{-1}^1 u_i'^{(q)}(\pm 1, \xi) d\xi, \quad \hat{t}_i^{(p,q)} = \frac{1}{2} \int_{-1}^1 t_i^{(q)}(\pm 1, \xi) d\xi \quad (8)$$

where traction $t_i^{(p,q)} = \sigma_{ij}^{(p,q)} n_j^{(p,q)}$ can be determined from Cauchy relation, and $\sigma_{ij}^{(p,q)}$ using to calculate $t_i^{(p,q)}$ can be derived from Hook's law $\sigma_{ij}^{(p,q)} = C_{ijkl}^{(q)} (\varepsilon_{kl} - \varepsilon_{kl}^{pl})^{(p,q)}$.

Therefore, in order to calculate the surface-averaged tractions, we need the surface-averaged strains which are partial derivatives of the surface-averaged displacement. The transform of the partial derivatives surface-averaged displacements in actual coordinates $y_2 - y_3$ and in reference coordinates $\eta - \xi$ is realized by applying the inverse of volume-averaged Jacobian, which allows us to write the surface-averaged interfacial displacements in terms of the 1st and 2nd order coefficients

$$\mathbf{W}_i = [W_{i(10)}, W_{i(01)}, W_{i(20)}, W_{i(02)}]^T$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial u_i'}{\partial y_2} \\ \frac{\partial u_i'}{\partial y_3} \end{bmatrix}^{(i)} = \hat{\mathbf{J}} \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial u_i'}{\partial \eta} \\ \frac{\partial u_i'}{\partial \xi} \end{bmatrix}^{(i)} = \hat{\mathbf{J}} \mathbf{A}_i \mathbf{W}_i \quad (9)$$

where

$$\mathbf{A}_{1,3} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & \pm 3 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{A}_{2,4} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & \pm 3 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

Then we apply the subvolume equations in a surface-average sense

$$\sum_{p=1}^4 \int_{L_p} \sigma^{(p,q)} \cdot \mathbf{n}^{(p,q)} dl = \sum_{p=1}^4 \int_{L_p} \mathbf{t}^{(p,q)} dl = \sum_{p=1}^4 L_p \hat{\mathbf{t}}^{(p,q)} = 0 \quad (11)$$

where L_p is the length of the p th face of the q th subvolume in the actual coordinates, the explicit expressions of \mathbf{W}_i in the q th subvolume can be derived in terms of fluctuating surface-averaged interfacial displacements.

The definitions of surface-averaged tractions can lead to the relationship between the surface-averaged tractions and surface-averaged fluctuating displacements. The final form of this relationship can be written in terms of the local stiffness matrix $\mathbf{K}^{(q)}$ for the q th subvolumes ($y_2^{(p,q)}, y_3^{(p,q)}$) of the q th subvolume

$$\hat{\mathbf{T}}^{(q)} = \mathbf{K}^{(q)} \hat{\mathbf{U}}^{r(q)} + \mathbf{N}^{(q)} \mathbf{C}^{(q)} \bar{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} + \mathbf{G}^{(q)} \quad (12)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{T}}^{(q)} = [\hat{\mathbf{t}}^{(1)} \hat{\mathbf{t}}^{(2)} \hat{\mathbf{t}}^{(3)} \hat{\mathbf{t}}^{(4)}]^{(q)T}$ and each element $\hat{\mathbf{t}}^{(p,q)} = [\hat{t}_1 \hat{t}_2 \hat{t}_3]^{(p,q)}$, $\hat{\mathbf{U}}^{r(q)} = [\hat{\mathbf{u}}^{r(1)} \hat{\mathbf{u}}^{r(2)} \hat{\mathbf{u}}^{r(3)} \hat{\mathbf{u}}^{r(4)}]^{(q)T}$ and each element $\hat{\mathbf{u}}^{r(p,q)} = [\hat{u}'_1 \hat{u}'_2 \hat{u}'_3]^{(p,q)}$, $\mathbf{N}^{(q)}$ represents the orientation of the subvolume surfaces, $\mathbf{G}^{(q)}$ contains vectors concerning plastic contributions. The local stiffness matrix $\mathbf{K}^{(q)}$ contains 16 submatrices $\mathbf{K}_{ij}^{(q)}$, and the submatrix $\mathbf{K}_{ij}^{(q)}$ is a 3×3 matrix derived by the subvolume geometry and material properties in closed form.

After introducing the displacement and traction continuity equation on the interfaces of adjacent subvolumes along columns and rows, the global system of equations can be determined

$$\mathbf{K}^{global} \hat{\mathbf{U}}^r = \Delta \mathbf{C} \bar{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} + \boldsymbol{\Gamma} + \mathbf{G} \quad (13)$$

By solving the above global governing equation, we can get displacement, strain and stress fields in each subvolume. The Hill's concentration matrix $\mathbb{A}^{(q)}$ for each subvolume can then be obtained by using the localization relation below

$$\bar{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^{(q)} = \mathbb{A}^{(q)} \bar{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} + \mathbb{D}^{(q)} \quad (14)$$

where each column vector of $\mathbb{A}^{(q)}$ can be obtained by applying one non-zero macroscopic strain component. $\mathbb{D}^{(q)}$ is path-dependent vector contains plastic contributions and can be calculated at each increment of the applied loading written in terms of the macroscopic strains $\bar{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}$ in the form of $\mathbb{D}^{(q)} = \bar{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^{(q)} - \mathbb{A}^{(q)} \bar{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}$.

The homogenized Hooke's law for the unit cell can be calculated by taking the volume average of the stresses field as below

$$\bar{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} = \frac{1}{V} \int \boldsymbol{\sigma}(x) dV = \frac{1}{V} \sum_{q=1}^{N_q} \int_{V_q} \bar{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}^{(q)}(x) dV^{(q)} = \sum_{q=1}^{N_q} v^{(q)} \bar{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}^{(q)} = \mathbf{C}^* (\bar{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} - \bar{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^{pl}) \quad (15)$$

where $v^{(q)} = V^{(q)} / V$ is the volume fraction of the q th subvolume, the homogenized stiffness matrix $\mathbf{C}^* = \sum_{q=1}^{N_q} v^{(q)} \bar{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}^{(q)} \mathbb{A}^{(q)}$ and $\bar{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^{pl} = [\mathbf{C}^*]^{-1} \sum_{k=1}^{N_k} v^{(k)} \mathbf{C}^{(k)} (\bar{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^{pl(k)} - \mathbb{D}^{(k)})$

The total plastic stain at each material point in the reference coordinates (η, ξ) consists of the contribution of the previous step and the contribution of current load increment

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{ij}^{pl(q)}(\eta, \xi) = \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{ij}^{pl(q)}(\eta, \xi) \Big|_{previous} + d\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{ij}^{pl(q)}(\eta, \xi) \quad (16)$$

where the plastic strain increment $d\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{ij}^{pl(q)}(\eta, \xi)$ is determined by the Abdel-Karim-Ohno constitutive model.

The cyclic plasticity simulation of wavy composites is achieved by introducing the Abdel-Karim-Ohno constitutive model into the calculation of the soft phase, the detail of which will be introduced in Section 3.

3 IMPLEMENTATION OF THE CYCLIC PLASTICITY MODEL

The model of wavy composites we build in this paper consists a hard elastic phase and a soft elastoplastic phase. After the discretization in Section 2, the aim of the model is to calculate the plastic strain incremental of each and every material points. In this work, the elastoplastic response of the soft phase is modeled using the Abdel-Karim-Ohno model[6].

The small strain of material points in the elastic hard phase obey the Hook's law which makes it very easy to calculate the strain incremental. For the points in the soft elastoplastic phase, the governing equation of Abdel-Karim-Ohno model should be applied and a return mapping should be used to obtain the plastic deformation. The governing equations are as follows

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^p \quad (17)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{C} : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e \quad (18)$$

$$\dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^p = \dot{\lambda} \frac{\partial F}{\partial \boldsymbol{\sigma}} \quad (19)$$

$$F = \sqrt{\frac{3}{2}(\mathbf{s} - \mathbf{a}) : (\mathbf{s} - \mathbf{a})} - Y \quad (20)$$

$$\mathbf{a} = \sum_{i=1}^N \mathbf{a}_i \quad (21)$$

$$\dot{\mathbf{a}}_i = \zeta_i \left[\frac{2}{3} r_i \dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^p - \mu_i \mathbf{a}_i \dot{p} \right] \quad (22)$$

$$\dot{\mathbf{a}}_i = \zeta_i \left[\frac{2}{3} r_i \dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^p - \mu_i \mathbf{a}_i \dot{p} - H(f_i) \langle \dot{\lambda}_i \rangle \mathbf{a}_i \right] \quad (23)$$

$$\dot{\lambda}_i = \dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^p : \frac{\mathbf{a}_i}{r_i} - \mu_i \dot{p} \quad (24)$$

$$\dot{p} = \sqrt{\frac{2}{3} \dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^p : \dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^p} \quad (25)$$

where strain $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ is assumed to be a sum of elastic deformation $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e$ and plastic deformation $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^p$, deviatoric back stresses \mathbf{a} are divided into N parts, \mathbf{s} are deviatoric parts of $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$, Eq. (20) represents the yield surface in the deviatoric space, where \mathbf{a} is the center and Y represents the radius, p stands for the accumulated plastic strain. ζ_i , μ_i and r_i are material parameters.

The goal is to calculate the plastic strain incremental $d\varepsilon_{ij}^{pl(q)}(\eta, \xi)$ for each material point which can then be implemented into Eq. (16) in Section 2. Therefore, for numerical implementation, Eq(17)-(25) should be discretized over time. After applying the method of return mapping, we can calculate the plastic strain at t_{n+1} using the known values of $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$, \mathbf{a} , $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$, $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^p$, p , Y at t_n . The plastic strain increment can then be easily derived.

With the increment of plastic strain of every material point in soft elastoplastic phase being calculated, the homogenized and localized response can be easily simulated using the FVDAM theory illustrated in Section 2.

3 NUMERICAL RESULTS

To simulate the response of the fiber reinforced and multilayer wavy composites, two different wavy unit cells with 0.3 hard phase volume fraction is built (see figure 3). The material properties are listed in Table 1 and Table 2. To examine the influence of the waviness, different amplitude-to-length ratio (A/L) are investigated under unidirectional strain controlled loading. The homogenized and localized responses of wavy composites are shown below.

Figure 2: Unit cells of two type of wavy composites with 0.3 hard phase volume fraction and 0.05 amplitude-to-length ratio.

	Hard phase	Soft phase
E / GPa	21.7	258
ν	20.3	850
Y / MPa	28.3	523

Table 1: Material properties for hard and soft phase.

Kinematic hardening parameters			
$\zeta^{(1)} = 2000$	$\zeta^{(2)} = 500$	$\zeta^{(3)} = 200$	$\zeta^{(4)} = 50$
$r^{(1)} = 50$	$r^{(2)} = 50$	$r^{(3)} = 50$	$r^{(4)} = 100$
$\mu = 0, 0.15, 1$			

Table 2: Kinematic hardening parameters of soft phase.

3.1 Local field distribution

In order to investigate how amplitude-to-length ratio (A/L) affects the local field, we present the local field of the effective plastic strain distributions of unit cell with different wavinesses ($A/L=0, 0.05$ and 0.1) at a macroscopic unidirectional strain of $\bar{\epsilon}_{22} = 1\%$ (see Figure 3). Two different wavy structures were investigated, fiber reinforced wavy composite in Figure 3 (left) and multilayer wavy composite in Figure 3 (right). As observed in Fig.3, waviness influences the local effective plastic strain field, which can affect the homogenized response of the composite materials.

For fiber reinforced wavy material, when $A/L=0$, we can see a continuous lighted plastic channel across the unit cell which means the local field distribution is uniform. However, with the increase of the waviness, the channel becomes discontinuous. When $A/L=0.15$, plastic channel breaks in the middle, which may lead to failure at material level.

For multilayer wavy material, since the distribution of hard phase is continuous in the unit cell, waviness has greater effect on the local field. By plotting the effective plastic strain field with the same scale of color bar. It can be observed that with the increase of the waviness, maximum value of effective plastic strain increases. The maximum plastic strain occurs at the largest slope region along the wavy interface of the hard and soft layer, which may lead to stress concentration and failure.

Figure 3: Effective plastic strain distributions in unit cells of two types of wavy materials with different amplitude-to-length ratio ($A/L=0, 0.05$ and 0.1) at $\bar{\epsilon}_{22} = 1\%$

3.2 Macroscopic cyclic behavior

The homogenized cyclic plasticity behavior under unidirectional strain loading is examined with different amplitude-to-length ratio ($A/L=0.05, 0.1$ and 0.15). Since the fiber reinforced material has the discontinuous hard phase distribution in the unit cell, the waviness has little influence on the macroscopic response. Therefore, we only present the macroscopic cyclic behavior of multilayer wavy material.

Figure 5(left) shows the applied transverse strain which varies from between 1% and 2% as a function of the incremental number. As shown in Figure 5 (right), the decrease of the waviness provide an enhancement in the elastic-plastic region while the elastic response almost remain the same. The phenomena of mean stress relaxation can be observed and it is closely related to the waviness. With the decrease of the waviness, this phenomena becomes more obvious.

Figure 4: Cyclic loading history (left) and cyclic response of multilayer wavy composite with 4 different waviness ($A/L=0.05, 0.1, 0.15, 0.2$) (right).

4 CONCLUSION

The waviness has a great influence on the homogenized and localized elastoplastic response of composite materials with wavy microstructures. In this work, two kinds of unit cell is built to represent the micro property of fiber reinforced wavy composite material and multilayer wavy composite material. The Abdel-Karim-Ohno constitutive model is implemented in the framework of the FVDAM theory, providing the ability of investigating the cyclic plastic response of the wavy composites.

In the local field, for fiber reinforced wavy composites, discontinuity of plastic channel occurs at large waviness, which may result in failure at material level. As for multilayer wavy composites, maximum value of effective plastic strain increases with the waviness and causing the stress concentration which may lead to material failure.

Transverse unidirectional cyclic strain loading between 1% to 2% is applied to investigate the homogenized cyclic response of multilayer wavy composites. The result shows that the mean stress relaxation phenomena is sensible to the waviness, decrease of the waviness provide an enhancement in the cyclic behavior.

The proposed model have proved to be an efficient tool in investigating the localized and homogenized elastoplastic response of wavy composites under cyclic loading which may provide some useful information for future material production.

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REFERENCES

- [1] H. Khatam, M.-J. Pindera, Thermo-elastic moduli of periodic multilayers with wavy architectures. *Composites Part B: Engineering*, **40**, 2009, pp.:50-64 (doi: [10.1016/j.compositesb.2008.07.001](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesb.2008.07.001)).
- [2] H. Khatam, M.-J. Pindera, Microstructural scale effects in the nonlinear elastic response of bio-inspired wavy multilayers undergoing finite deformation. *Composites Part B: Engineering*, **43**, 2012, pp.:869-84 (doi: [10.1016/j.compositesb.2011.11.032](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesb.2011.11.032)).
- [3] H. Khatam, M.-J. Pindera, Plasticity-triggered architectural effects in periodic multilayers with wavy microstructures. *International Journal of Plasticity*, **26**, 2010, pp.:273-87 (doi: [10.1016/j.ijplas.2009.06.002](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijplas.2009.06.002)).
- [4] A. Katz, C. Trinh, J. Wright, W. Tu, M.-J. Pindera, Plastic strain localization in periodic materials with wavy brick-and-mortar architectures and its effect on the homogenized response. *Composites Part B: Engineering*, **68**, 2015, pp.:270-80 (doi: [10.1016/j.compositesb.2014.08.037](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesb.2014.08.037)).
- [5] W. Tu, M.-J. Pindera, Targeting the finite-deformation response of wavy biological tissues with bio-inspired material architectures. *Journal of the Mechanical Behavior of Biomedical Materials*, **28**, 2013, pp.:291-308 (doi: [10.1016/j.jmbbm.2013.08.001](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmbbm.2013.08.001)).
- [6] M. Abdel-Karim, N. Ohno, Kinematic hardening model suitable for ratchetting with steady-state. *International Journal of Plasticity*, **16**, 2000, pp.:225-40 (doi: [10.1016/S0749-6419\(99\)00052-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0749-6419(99)00052-2)).
- [7] Y. Bansal, M.-J. Pindera, Finite-volume direct averaging micromechanics of heterogeneous materials with elastic-plastic phases. *International Journal of Plasticity*, **22**, 2006, pp.:775-825 (doi: [10.1016/j.ijplas.2005.04.012](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijplas.2005.04.012)).
- [8] M. Gattu, H. Khatam, A.S. Drago, M.-J. Pindera, Parametric finite-volume micromechanics of uniaxial continuously-reinforced periodic materials with elastic phases. *Journal of Engineering Materials and Technology*, **130**, 2008, pp.:031015 (doi: [10.1115/1.2931157](https://doi.org/10.1115/1.2931157)).
- [9] H. Khatam, M.J. Pindera, Parametric finite-volume micromechanics of periodic materials with elastoplastic phases. *International Journal of Plasticity*, **25**, 2009, pp.:1386-411 (doi: [10.1016/j.ijplas.2008.09.003](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijplas.2008.09.003)).
- [10] M.A.A. Cavalcante, M.J. Pindera, H. Khatam, Finite-volume micromechanics of periodic materials: Past, present and future. *Composites Part B*, **43**, 2012, pp.:2521-43 (doi: [10.1016/j.compositesb.2012.02.006](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesb.2012.02.006)).
- [11] Q. Chen, G. Wang, Homogenized and localized responses of coated magnetostrictive porous materials and structures. *Composite Structures*, **187**, 2018, pp.:102-15 (doi: [10.1016/j.compstruct.2017.12.032](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2017.12.032)).
- [12] N. Charalambakis, Homogenization techniques and micromechanics. A survey and perspectives. *Applied Mechanics Reviews*, **63**, 2010, pp.:030803--10 (doi: [10.1115/1.4001911](https://doi.org/10.1115/1.4001911)).